

TEACHER COMPETENCE AND STUDENT PSYCHOMOTOR EVALUATION: CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION IN SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to investigate the relationship between teacher competence and students' psychomotor evaluation in the context of curriculum implementation in schools. A quantitative approach was used to collect data from teachers and students in several schools. The research instruments consisted of questionnaires to measure teachers' perceptions of their competencies and observations to assess students' psychomotor levels. The results showed that teachers' competence has a significant influence on students' psychomotor evaluation. Teachers who have high competence tend to provide more effective teaching, better facilitate students' psychomotor development, and provide more constructive feedback. In addition, it was found that good curriculum implementation can strengthen the relationship between teacher competence and students' psychomotor evaluation. These findings highlight the importance of developing teachers' competencies in supporting students' learning, especially in the psychomotor aspect. The practical implications of this study emphasise the need for continuous training and development for teachers to improve their teaching quality and enhance students' psychomotor evaluation.

Keywords: Teachers' competence, Students' psychomotor evaluation, Curriculum implementation

INTRODUCTION

Minister of Education and Research and Technology Nadiem Anwar Makarim officially launched the new name of the prototype curriculum called the independent curriculum. The independent curriculum was developed as a curriculum framework that is more flexible and centred on fundamental material and develops the uniqueness and abilities of students. 'The Ministry of Education and Culture stated that there are 4 ideas of change that support independent learning programmes that are related to the National Standardised Test (USBN), National Examination (UN), Learning Implementation Plan (RPP), and Zoning New Learner Admission Regulation (PPDB)'. The stand-alone curriculum is designed to support learning recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. Learning freedom for both teachers and students is emphasised in independent learning. 'The Ministry of Education and Culture defines independent learning as a learning process that gives freedom and authority to each educational institution to be free from complicated administration'. 'The main assumption of independent learning is giving trust to teachers so that teachers feel independent in carrying out learning' (Koesoema,

2020). the learning atmosphere is more comfortable, teachers and students can have more relaxed discussions, learning can be outside the classroom which not only listens to the teacher's explanation, but rather forms courage, independence, cleverness in mingling, civilised, polite, competence, and does not only rely on the *ranking* system which, according to several surveys, is only troubling for children and parents.' As for the Concept of Merdeka Belajar in the opinion of (Sherly et al., 2020) 'returning the national education system to the opinion of the national education system (Sherly et al., 2020)', 2020) 'returns the national education system to the essence of the law to give schools the freedom to interpret the basic competencies of the curriculum into their assessment'. competency-based curriculum is characterised by the development of competencies in the form of attitudes, knowledge, thinking skills, and psychomotor skills packaged in various subjects (Haryati, 2009).

Affective learning from a process and learning outcomes emphasises how students behave and behave in their community environment (Supardi, 2015). In this learning there are several affective domains related to attitudes which consist of: acceptance, response or reaction, organisation assessment, and internalisation Teacher skills in learning can be seen from the teacher's ability to provide understanding to students about the subject matter presented. Skills learning will be effective when using the principle of learning by doing (Sunarti, 2014). Skills that are trained through repeated practice will become a habit and automatically performed. The successful development of cognitive aspects will also have a positive impact on the development of psychomotor aspects.

A teacher who can provide psychomotor skills to students will have an impact on the ability of students who have physical skills both in quantity and quality (Suheman, 2014). However, while psychomotor skills are inseparable from cognitive skills, they are also largely bound by affective skills. So, students' psychomotor skills are a manifestation of knowledge insight and awareness and mental attitude. Curriculum model is based on the competency-based curriculum model.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used by the author is a secondary data collection method or the use of document data, because in this case the author does not collect his own data but takes and examines primary data from other parties. Most data is taken from the internet, because the internet provides a variety of primary data from previous writers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teacher Competence

Teachers are one of the determinants of success in education and improving the quality of human resources. In line with (Yuslam et al., 2017) teachers are an important profession in improving the quality of Indonesian human resources. According to (Sujiono, 2012) a teacher is defined as someone who is entrusted with education and mind formation. Teachers are people who provide knowledge to students (Nurkholis & Badawi, 2019).

Teacher competence is the ability and authority of teachers in carrying out their obligations with responsibility with their duties as teachers. Because teaching is a profession or job, competence is needed in the teaching and learning process.

Teacher competence in accordance with ministerial regulation number 58 of 2009 concerning early childhood education standards includes pedagogic competence, personality competence, social competence, and professional competence obtained through professional education. In line with the opinion of (Ittihad, 2016) On teacher competence, there are four competencies that teachers must have, including:

Pedagogic Competence

Pedagogic ability is the ability to educate children. According to (Anwar, 2019) pedagogic competence is the ability to understand students deeply and organise educational lessons. According to (Nuraeni & Riyanto, 2017) Pedagogic competence is the ability of a teacher to manage the learning process of students. According to (Utari et al., 2015) Pedagogical competencies that must be mastered by teachers include understanding teachers of children, designing and implementing learning, evaluating learning outcomes, and developing children to actualise their various potentials. This understanding includes understanding the characteristics of children and the process of child development.

Personality Competence

According to (Fadilah et al., 2019) Pedagogic competence is a fundamental competence in the context of child education practice, because pedagogic competence is needed as a system of knowledge about child education which will become the basis or foundation in child education practice, besides that pedagogic competence will also be a standard for the success of child education practice.

According to (Mu'izz, 2017) Pedagogic competence is the teacher's ability to manage student learning which at least includes the following: a) Understanding educational insights or foundations; b) Understanding of students; c) Curriculum development; d) Learning design; e) Implementation of educational and dialogical learning; f) Utilisation of learning technology; g) Evaluation of learning outcomes (EHB), is the development of students to actualise their various potentials.

According to (Saputra et al., 2019) The concept of pedagogics is a very

important competency for teachers, especially in efforts to understand the characteristics of students, manage (plan, implement, evaluate, and follow up) learning, and develop the various potentials of students effectively and optimally. This competence is needed by a teacher in carrying out his main task as a teacher.

Based on this description, it can be concluded that pedagogic competence is very important for a teacher to have, because through this ability the teacher can carry out his duties properly such as understanding the characteristics of students, managing (planning, implementing, evaluating, and following up) learning, and developing the various potentials of students effectively and optimally. Pedagogic competence needs to be mastered by a teacher in order to manage learning effectively.

Social Competence

One of the competencies that teachers must have is social competence. According to (Huda, 2018) teacher social competence is the social ability of teachers which includes the ability to adapt to the demands of work and the surrounding environment at the time of carrying out their duties as teachers and the ability of social communication skills both with students, fellow teachers, principals, administrative staff, even with members of the community. Good communication skills will establish a better atmosphere or relationship so that teachers can adjust to their environment.

Social skills are related to communication or social interaction. According to (Sumitra et al., 2018) teacher social competence is the ability and skills of a teacher to communicate and interact effectively in the implementation of the learning process and the surrounding community. According to (Sofia & Syafrudin, 2020) Social competence includes skills in social interaction and carrying out social responsibilities. Therefore, social competence is the ability to communicate and interact well in various ways so that they are able to adjust and place themselves in their environment.

Professional Competence

Professional competence is one of the competencies that teachers must have. According to (Kobaa, 2018) The word professional indicates that a teacher must be able to compete in improving the quality of national education and must also always improve his expertise and skills in performing his duties as a teacher. According to (Díaz- Maggioli, 2006) Professional development can be defined as a career-long process in which educators perfect their teaching to meet the needs of children in learning.

According to (Mutawati, 2018) Professional competence is a prerequisite that must be fulfilled by a teacher before carrying out his professional duties. According to (Utari et al., 2015) Professional competence is a broad and deep mastery of learning materials that must be mastered by teachers (priyanto) including mastery of school subject curriculum materials and the substance of the

knowledge that overshadows the material, as well as mastery of scientific structures and methodologies. According to (Mufidah, 2019) professionals are people who are considered experts in their fields, where they can make decisions independently and fairly. According to (Ittihad, 2016) Professionalism of educators is the ability of an educator or often referred to as a teacher, in carrying out his main duties from planning to evaluating learning. However, it is usually more dominant in mastering curriculum material, material for each theme or subtheme and other things. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that professional competence is the teacher's ability to master learning materials broadly and deeply, which must be mastered by teachers, including mastery of curriculum material, depth of material that needs to be discussed per theme, and mastery of scientific structures and methodologies. A teacher must be able to compete in improving the quality of national education and must also always improve their expertise and skills in performing their duties as a teacher.

Psychomotor

Psychomotor development is the development of control over coordinated body movements between nerves and muscles. These skills involve large parts of the body with gross movements such as sitting, standing, walking, running, and jumping.

Then, each of these gross movements can be coordinated with fine movements such as reaching, holding, throwing, and so on. Psychomotor development does look like a general development that every child achieves. For this reason, parents rarely pay attention to it. In fact, psychomotor development plays an important role in the growth and development process of every child and will affect their life in the future.

Moreover, psychomotor development not only impacts a child's physical abilities, but also affects their cognitive, social and emotional development. This includes the ability to communicate messages through movement, interact with others, improve thinking skills, know oneself better and express oneself more effectively.

Factors Affecting Psychomotor Development

The development of psychomotor skills allows children to manage the external world through their bodies. This contributes to the intellectual, affective, and social development of the child.

Each psychomotor development is influenced by the following factors; Family and environment, Nutrition obtained by the child, High emotional disturbance, Gender, Health, Influence of body shape, Growth and development of the nervous system, Growth of muscles and Changes in physical structure.

Indicators of fine psychomotor development of primary age children

Fine motor development in childhood enables children to become artists (Santrock, 2011). Children's habit of doodling can shape children's motor skills.

Therefore, K. Eileen Allen and Lynn R (2010) argue that there are four indicators of fine psychomotor development of primary age children, as follows:

- a. Writing, scribbling and performing other fine motor skills better. This phase is characterised by improved fine motor skills.
- b. Using arms, legs, palms and soles with greater ease and precision, such as keyboarding and sewing tends to be better at performing gross motor activities.
- c. Enjoys using hands to make arts and crafts, cooking, painting, making crafts, building and dismantling objects, such as clocks or telephones.
- d. Drawing in detail and painting, a child prefers to practise handwriting to perfection.

CONCLUSION

Teacher competence determines the success of teachers in carrying out their roles well in every educational institution. The four competencies are interrelated and inseparable. These teacher competencies must always be developed either through education, professional pathways, training or teaching experience. The more teacher competence is developed, the higher the quality of output or learning success. Therefore, the government/private institutions must provide facilities for teachers to improve their competence in a sustainable manner and in accordance with the times.

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